

Assessment of Reading Habits between Male and Female English Students in Federal College of Education Kano State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This research assessed reading habits between male and female English students in Federal College of Education Kano State. This study adopted survey research method with a total population of 420. With the aid of simple sampling techniques, 172 was sampled and participated in the study. The researchers administered 210 questionnaires but after editing and those with incomplete or unlikely response were rejected final copies utilized were 172. Chi-square was used to analyze the data obtained. The result shows that habits follow gender line with regards to the time spent for reading. The paper concluded that both male and female students were involved in reading and sex was found to be influential in the time and duration they choose to read. It is therefore recommended that provision of light in the evening be improved from 3 hours to six so as to encourage all students to read more

Keywords: Reading, Habit, Gender, Academic success.

Introduction

Undergraduate students on campuses across the nation read in order to pass their exams. For this to happen, however, decisions have to be taken as to where to read, what time to read and how much time to spend reading as their reading habits has become a tropical issue for school authorities. Therefore, the pertinent questions here are: “where do undergraduates students living in the campus prefer to go to and read? What time of the day and for how long?” A typical campus may provide an array of places that encourage students to go to read, but students are known to improvise places that are either inconvenient or devoid of necessary facilities. A serious undergraduate student has long discovered the importance of reading since secondary school days. Reading is indeed essential not only for academic success but also for intellectual growth, Steve (2018). However, reading requires sustained, focused attention that demands powers of memory and imagination. It is quite unlike watching television, video games or even surfing the internet that are considered passive activities. In fact, reading forces the individual to think as he works his brain out, while watching only allows him to escape. Reading therefore cannot be said to be an easy job at all. Perhaps as a result of this, college of education students of nowadays do not seem to read as much as they should. Consequently, they do not seem to believe in the role that reading plays in the development of one’s life, including academic success on the campus.

Ideally, College of education students are supposed to read hard in order to pass their exams. Evidence from campuses however suggests that the amount of reading they engage in leaves much to be desired (Besty, 2015). Lecturers across the nation have raised alarm at various fora about the unpreparedness of students before lectures

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and even during exams. Reading assignments during sessions are equally not taken seriously by the students, and submission dates for term papers and assignments are widely flouted with impunity. The refrain, not only in Nigeria but worldwide, is that this generation of students are not exactly serious when it comes to reading. These students are strangers to point of reference and underlying cadences that govern the development of written English (Charles, 2020). Although there is little research on students' reading and studying habits, many students have characteristics that put them at risk of academic failure. David (2016), said many of them find themselves in the colleges of education without the necessary skills to read or write even simple composition. And neither is their comprehension any better. However, this situation should not be allowed to continue and efforts to redress must be explored. Among these is the need to first understand the reading habits of these students.

One other reason for the fall in reading habit is said to be the distractions faced by students all over the country. Peter (2021) opined that recreational activities like sport and passive ones like TV and video games have indeed eaten deep into the spare time of students. So does the advent of the cell phone and the internet. Add these to the additional responsibilities heaped on students and the reason for inadequate reading will be pretty obvious. But Esther (2013), found the opposite to be true. Students do have tremendous leeway in their leisure activities and do have sufficient time available to study. According to this researcher, students are choosing not to spend time reading or studying by engaging in escapist activities like chatting on the net, then watching TV and playing video games. As a direct result of this, many students today are not strong readers and they regularly report that they don't like to read. And this apply to both leisure and for exams reading.

Poor reading habits at tertiary institutions may have deep causes that go back to early childhood experiences. The ability to read cannot be acquired overnight much less sustaining it over time. Studies have shown that catching them young may be the best strategy to inculcate sustainable reading habits. Dickson (2017) found that children who were already readers prior to beginning school came from homes in which literacy was engaged. He stated that one activity that was consistently found in the home of early readers was reading. Such children therefore came from homes in which family members read and one in which the children were read to and encouraged to read on regular basis. Lami, (2018) said this habit once internalized translate into a lifelong ability to read. It follows then that where this early childhood training was not developed, individuals would have little or no tendency to read. This may be one of the reasons for the non-reading behavior of college of education students in Nigeria today. Commenting on the reading habits of American students in the Washington Post, Charles (2010) wrote that "we have a generation of young adults away from home for the first time, free to enjoy the most experimental place of their lives, yet they are choosing books like 13 years old girl". But at least they are reading something when compare to most Nigeria NCE students who hardly read at all.

The blame for poor reading habits may not be heaped on parents alone. Schools equally share some portion of the blame. Schools needs to encourage students to do voluntary recreational reading which in itself can foster academic reading. Monsteve (2017) and Lami (2018), argue that low level of voluntary reading may be due to the fact that most school reading instructions are oriented to skill building and preparation for standardized tests with little overt reading for enjoyment. To the best knowledge of the researchers, not much research has been conducted on the reading habits and behaviour of college of education students in the country (Gimba, 2011). However, it is well known that reading is the cornerstone for success not just academically but throughout life. A study conducted by Gimba (2011), found evidence that supported this assumption and established correlation between reading and Cumulative Grade Point Average (CGPA) for students of both sexes. However, despite the obvious implication of this finding, concerns have been raised in several quarters about the declining reading habits by college of education students in Nigeria. Extant studies conducted by Muri (2016) showed students' inadequate reading and study skills among both public and private tertiary institutions. This trend appears to be worldwide as complaints emanate from all countries. The inadequacy in reading affects not only reading for leisure but also for academic success. On campuses across the nation, there seems to be a latent belief among students that one can as well pass exams without doing much reading (John, 2016). A little reading, the cliché goes, could just be enough to see one through his exams (Lami, 2018). Indeed, a common observation by many lecturers is that students do not seem particularly

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motivated to read on a regular basis. Many students come to class unprepared and more often than not postpone any reading until the night before the exam. This problem is irritating and frustrating for many teachers and school administrators. It is against the above backdrop that this study investigates where, when and for how long students in College of Education Kano read. These points could serve as a starting point for any action towards encouraging students to read more in our colleges of education.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of this study is to determine the reading habits of male and female students of English in Federal College of Kano. The specific objectives are

1. to identify the preferred reading place among male and female English students in Federal College of Education
2. to examine the preferred reading duration among male and female English students in Federal College of Education.
3. To determine the preferred reading time among male and female English students in Federal College of Education

Research Questions

1. What is the preferred reading place among male and female English students in Federal College of Education?
2. What is the preferred reading duration among male and female English students in Federal College of Education?
3. What is the preferred reading time among male and female English students in Federal College of Education?

Research Hypotheses

Based on the above objectives of the study, the following hypotheses were framed for the study:

1. H₀₁: There is no significant different on preferred reading place between male and female English students in Federal College of Education
2. H₀₂: There is no significant difference on preferred reading duration between male and female English students in Federal College of Education
3. H₀₃: There is no significant difference on preferred reading time between male and female English students in Federal College of Education?

Methodology

The final year NCE students of school of languages in first semester of 2021 represented the population and were surveyed. Being in their final year, this body of students were thought to be the most avid readers in the school of languages. School has an enrolment of 210 students in year 300 levels in four areas of specialization namely: English, Hausa, Arabic and French. Therefore, the population of the study consists of 300 level English students during the 2021/2022 academic session. A questionnaire was developed for this study and 15 minutes is required for its filling. Copies of the questionnaire were distributed during class place. The students were first briefed about the research and were assured that their responses would remain anonymous and confidential. The copies of the questionnaire were given out and collected back after completion before the end of the class place. A total of 4 questions were completed by each student. The data were summarized and percentages were calculated. Chi-square test was also carried out on the data for three of the questions with a view to finding whether significant relationship exists between male and female on the one hand and place, time and place for reading, on the other. Descriptive statistics was used to answer research questions while inferential statistics of chi-square was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The alpha value was set at 5% or 0.05 and the P-value provided. The usual decision rule for chi-square test applies to this study. That is we accept the null hypothesis (H₀) or reject the alternate hypothesis (H₁) if calculated value is less than the table value, and we reject the H₀ and accept the H₁ if the calculated value is greater than the table value.

Results

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference on preferred reading place between male and female English students in Federal College of Education

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Table 1: Chi-Square Test of difference on preferred reading place between male and female English students

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	8.000 ^a	1	.938
Likelihood Ratio	8.318	1	.216
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.640	1	.200
N of Valid Cases	2		

a. 12 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .25.

Source: Author's Computation using SPSS version 20.0, 2023

The chi-square critical value at 5% level of significance obtained from the chi-square mathematical and statistical table is 0.0039. Since the Pearson chi-square value which is 0.938 is greater than the chi-square critical value at 5% level of significance which is 0.0039, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference on preferred reading place between male and female English students in Federal College of Education. Since we rejected the null hypothesis and accepted the alternative hypothesis, we conclude that there is significant difference between reading habits of male and female English students and their preferred place for reading. This means a reading habits of male and female English students does not dictate the place where a student goes to read.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference on the preferred reading duration between male and female English student in Federal College of Education.

Table 2: Chi-Square Test of difference on the preferred reading duration between male and female English student

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	8.000 ^a	1	.724
Likelihood Ratio	8.318	1	.216
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.640	1	.200
N of Valid Cases	2		

a. 12 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .25.

Source: Author's Computation using SPSS version 20.0, 2023

The chi-square critical value at 5% level of significance obtained from the chi-square mathematical and statistical table is 0.0039. Since the Pearson chi-square value which is 0.724 is greater than the chi-square critical value at 5% level of significance which is 0.0039, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference on the preferred reading duration between male and female English student in Federal College of Education. Since we rejected the null hypothesis and accepted the alternate hypothesis, we conclude that there is significant differences between reading habits of male and female English students and their preferred time for reading. This means a reading habits of male and female English students dictates the time of the day or night when he or she goes to read.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant different between male and female students of English and the amount of time spent reading.

Table 3: Chi-Square Test different between male and female students of English and the amount of time spent reading

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	8.000 ^a	1	.801
Likelihood Ratio	8.318	1	.216
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.640	1	.245
N of Valid Cases	2		

a. 12 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .25.

Source: Author's Computation using SPSS version 20.0, 2023

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The chi-square critical value at 5% level of significance obtained from the chi-square mathematical and statistical table is 0.0039. Since the Pearson chi-square value which is 0.801 is greater than the chi-square critical value at 5% level of significance which is 0.0039, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between male and female students' of English and the amount of time spent reading. Since we rejected the null hypothesis and accepted the alternate hypothesis, we conclude that there is significant difference between reading habits of male and female English students and the amount of time they spend reading. The alternate hypothesis is therefore rejected.

Discussion of Findings

The null hypothesis one which states that there is no significant relationship between reading habits of male and female English students' and their preferred place for reading was accepted after Chi-square test. The test revealed that the calculated value χ^2 (0.938) was less than the table value (0.0039) and therefore we reject the null hypothesis. In other words, reading habits of male and female English students does not dictate where students go to read. This finding is in line with Leary (2014) who opined that male and female place of reading has no significant bearing with their academic performance.

The null hypothesis two which states that there is no significant relationship between reading habits of male and female English students and their preferred time for reading was rejected after Chi-square test. The test revealed that the calculated value χ^2 (0.724) was greater than the table value (0.0039); we reject the null hypothesis. In other words, reading habits of male and female English students dictates the time of the day when students go to read. This finding is also in line with the research conducted by Gimba (2011) who concluded that male and female English students determine the time to read.

Null hypothesis three which states that there is no significant relationship between reading habits of male and female English students and the amount of time spent reading was accepted after the Chi-square test. The test revealed that the calculated value of χ^2 (0.801) was less than the table value (0.0039) we reject the null hypothesis. In other words, reading habits of male and female English students does not dictate the amount of time students spent reading. However, this finding is slightly different from the research conducted by lami (2018) who concluded that reading habit of male and female do dictate to some extent the amount of time students spends reading

Conclusion

This paper set out to assess the reading habits of students of English language, Federal college of Education Kano. Both male and female students were involved and gender was found to be influential in the time they chose to study, but not so with regard to place and amount of time they spent reading. It appears that girls preferred evenings for their reading while boys preferred night time. This implies that overall, students prefer to read between 6:00pm to midnight, a place that necessarily requires availability of light.

Recommendations

Based on the above, the following recommendations are made;

1. School authorities should endeavor to make light available during this peak place for reading. This should be from 6:00pm to at least 11:00pm so as to allow a six hours stretch. Such a stretch will go a long way in encouraging more reading among students.
2. School can successfully encourage reading generally by initiating school based programmes in which time is set aside daily for compulsory leisure and academic reading.
3. conducive atmosphere must readily be made available.

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